

FEATURES OF MODERN DIPLOMATIC SERVICE AS AN IMPORTANT COMPONENT OF THE DIPLOMATIC ACTIVITY OF THE STATE

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Abstract: The relevance of the study of modern diplomatic service lies in view of the constantly changing trends in the development of world politics and international relations. At the moment, the modern political environment is constantly changing, including the increasing role of non-state actors, changes in the global economy and the emergence of new challenges such as cybersecurity and climate change. The purpose of the research in this scientific article is to reveal the main features of the modern diplomatic service as an important component of the diplomatic activity of the state. The advantages of modern diplomacy include the non-use of military methods for resolving interstate conflicts, increasing the role of strategic and economic partnerships, and achieving compromise approaches to resolving issues related to states (climate, economy, transit routes). As practice has shown, it was a peaceful and economically thoughtful approach in relations between states that made it possible to achieve progress in many areas of relations between states. The research methodology covers the use of such methods of scientific knowledge as analysis, synthesis, induction, deduction, generalization, modeling and forecasting the development of diplomatic activity and service in the future. The research conducted by the author allows us to identify the features of modern diplomacy and, at the theoretical and legal level, to develop more effective strategies for the development of many types of diplomacy, which is extremely important in the context of globalization, when solving international problems requires a coordinated approach from different countries. Particular importance should be given to digital diplomacy, and strengthening the role of society in communication both within one state and within two or more states, through identifying and studying the opinion of society in approaches to solving many problems. Modern diplomacy is primarily distinguished by an information and communication approach in interstate communication, as well as in interaction with society. Thus, the combination of many types of diplomacy (for example, public and digital diplomacy) will be more effective, amenable to theoretical and legal research and predictable from the point of view of improving the diplomatic service.

Key words: diplomacy, diplomatic service, diplomat, activity, strategy, foreign policy, state.

Introduction

Diplomatic activity in the modern world remains a key tool for interaction between states. The relevance of the theoretical justification for the expansion of diplomatic activities in a modern state lies in the fact that they replace outdated, unjustified military and aggressive methods of solving foreign policy problems [Tursunova, 2023].

The relevance of the study of modern diplomatic service lies in view of the constantly changing trends in the development of world politics and international relations. The current political environment is constantly changing, including the increasing role of non-state actors, changes in the global economic balance and the emergence of new challenges such as cybersecurity and climate change. Foreign service research helps to understand how these changes are affecting international relations and how diplomats are adapting their practices to effectively respond to these challenges.

In the modern world, the importance of soft power, including cultural exchange, education and humanitarian assistance, is increasing. Conducting appropriate research makes it possible to clarify the effectiveness of these methods for identifying new opportunities for the development of international relations and conflict resolution. As practice has shown, it was a peaceful and economically thoughtful approach in relations between states that made it possible to achieve progress in many areas of relations between states. Here we note the need to study the diplomatic service to understand the impact of cross-border challenges, such as international terrorism, migration flows and pandemics, on diplomatic activity and ways to overcome them.

The purpose of the research in this scientific article is to reveal the main features of the modern diplomatic service as an important component of the diplomatic activity of the state. The study allows us to identify many features of diplomacy and develop more effective strategies for conducting foreign policy, which is extremely important in the context of globalization, when solving international problems requires a coordinated approach from different countries. Accordingly, the study of contemporary foreign service is important for adapting strategies and maintaining effective practices in conducting international relations in the face of ever-changing challenges and opportunities.

The objectives of the study are determined by the stated goal and are related to the theoretical and legal characteristics of the diplomatic service and activities.

The research methodology covers the use of such methods of scientific knowledge as analysis, synthesis, induction, deduction, generalization, modeling and forecasting the development of diplomatic activity and service in the future.

Issues of the development of the diplomatic service as a separate special type of public service were the subject of research by such authors as M.U. Tursunova, Sh.Sh. Takhirov, M.S. Glebov, V.G. Seidov, O.E. Kuzina, R.S. . John, J. Valuch and others.

Results

Modern diplomatic activities are sets of work practices of state representatives and consuls that require certain human resources[Glebov, 2018]. An important priority of foreign policy and cooperation with many states is the development of human capital [Speech by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 2022], strengthening cooperation between countries in multiple spheres of society [Speech by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 2022].

With the increasing complexity of international relations, diplomacy has become increasingly important to ensure peace, stability and development. The state and characteristics of diplomatic activity have shaped such an area of legal knowledge and profession as the diplomatic service, which is an organizational and legal system of activities of professional diplomats working on behalf of a state or an international organization to ensure external relations and cooperation between different countries. The main features of

the diplomatic service include representation, through which diplomats act on behalf of their states and perform the functions of representation in the international arena.

In the modern understanding, diplomatic activity is represented in the priority and strategic activities of heads of state, government and special bodies of external relations to implement the goals and objectives of the foreign policy of states, as well as to protect the interests of the state abroad. Public diplomatic activity involves building long-term relationships [Seidov, 2017]. It should be taken into account that a state that does not have attractive values is not able to influence foreign society through public diplomacy [John, 2003].

The main task of diplomatic activity within the framework of professional service is to protect the national interests of one's country, including negotiating, concluding treaties and agreements. Diplomats collect, analyze and transmit information about political, economic and other events in the host country, and together they form a system of professional employees working in the Ministry of Foreign Affairs, diplomatic missions or embassies involved in ensuring the external relations of the state. Diplomatic missions can provide sources of information, which has a special status, since diplomatic employees are located directly in the country of accreditation [Valuch, 2011].

Today, in many countries, diplomats work to ensure the protection of the interests of their state abroad. They also participate in establishing and maintaining diplomatic relations between their state and other countries, and conduct negotiations with representatives of other states on various issues such as trade, security, economic cooperation, etc. The means of public diplomacy can provide states with additional opportunities to achieve the necessary foreign policy objectives, which leads to their active use in foreign policy practice by many leading states [Kuzina, 2020].

The modern diplomatic service is a comprehensive system of international relations based on establishing and maintaining interaction between states, international organizations and other participants in the world community. The main features of the modern diplomatic service include:

1. Multifunctionality, since the diplomatic service today performs a wide range of functions, including representing the interests of its state abroad, participation in international negotiations and agreements, consular services for citizens, development of economic and cultural relations and other tasks;

2. The use of new communication technologies, when modern diplomats actively use modern technologies to improve communication, analyze information, and conduct virtual negotiations. But at the same time, we must not forget about the need to technically improve cybersecurity in digital communications of states and their representative institutions (diplomatic missions);

3. Emphasis on soft power, as the Foreign Service increasingly places emphasis on the use of soft power in the form of cultural exchange, civil society development, education, and humanitarian assistance to achieve foreign policy goals;

4. Global nature, due to which modern diplomacy faces more complex and global challenges, such as climate change, international terrorism and migration, which requires diplomats to have a broader and more flexible approach to solving problems. Today, the need to organize joint efforts of states to solve climate change problems is becoming particularly

global, which cannot be effectively implemented without an effectively functioning diplomatic service and constant dialogue between states.

The diplomatic service is implemented through a wide range of activities, including the representation of the interests of the state. Diplomatic representatives abroad act as the main implementers of the foreign policy of their state. They maintain contacts with representatives of other countries, international organizations and non-governmental organizations, and also conduct negotiations on issues important to their state.

Diplomatic missions also carry out consular activities, providing assistance to their citizens abroad, for example in case of emergencies, loss of documents or legal support. Diplomats participate in international negotiations on a wide range of issues, from peacekeeping to trade. They represent the interests of their state and contribute to the achievement of mutually beneficial agreements. For example, consular officers may provide assistance to nationals of their country who are in a foreign country and facing problems, such as the need for medical care or support in case of problems with the law. Diplomats can also participate in international negotiations for trade agreements or peace treaties, representing the interests of their state and making constructive contributions to the process of international cooperation.

It should be noted that in 2017, the bill "On the Diplomatic Service of the Republic of Uzbekistan" was presented in Uzbekistan. The content of this bill defines special regulatory grounds for the organization of the diplomatic service of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the purpose of which is to implement the foreign policy of the state in accordance with the Concept of foreign policy activities of the Republic of Uzbekistan [Takhirov, 2022]. The adoption of this Law in the near future seems to be an urgent law-making task, which will improve the status of the diplomatic service, increase the corresponding personnel apparatus of the diplomatic service and the image of the country.

Conclusion

The practical directions of the modern diplomatic service are, first of all, the representative, multifunctional and multidisciplinary activities of diplomatic missions and consular offices. The classification of the diplomatic service based on areas is most appropriate when analyzing the strategic goal setting of a particular government in the implementation of public diplomacy of the state. At the same time, it is necessary to highlight such areas of the diplomatic service as political and economic diplomacy, consular activities, cultural and information diplomacy. Particularly popular in this classification is digital diplomacy, which is actively developing in the media sphere and social networks.

Great importance should be attached to many types of diplomacy, the development and improvement of which are priority and strategic directions for effective interaction between states. In particular, public diplomacy, since in the modern information society public diplomacy, based on influencing public opinion and cultural exchange, is becoming increasingly important. The development of media strategies, the use of social networks and active work with public organizations are becoming key aspects of the development of public diplomacy.

At the same time, enhancing mutual understanding and peaceful coexistence through cultural and educational exchanges becomes more meaningful in a world divided by many differences. Developing and improving this type of diplomacy includes creating and

maintaining cultural programs, student exchanges, humanitarian assistance and other initiatives that promote peaceful interaction.

In the context of globalization, economic diplomacy is becoming increasingly important. The development and improvement of this type of diplomacy is associated with the search for new markets, attracting investment, securing trade advantages and cooperation in the field of economics, technology and innovation. Along with this, the rapid development of digital communications and technologies requires the development of new approaches and methods of conducting foreign policy. Digital diplomacy includes the use of digital channels to interact with citizens and diplomatic partners, as well as addressing cybersecurity and digital trust. Particular importance should be given to digital diplomacy, and strengthening the role of society in communication both within one state and within two or more states, through identifying and studying the opinion of society in approaches to solving many problems. Thus, the combination of many types of diplomacy (for example, public and digital diplomacy) will be more effective, amenable to theoretical and legal research and predictable from the point of view of improving the diplomatic service.

The development and improvement of these types of diplomacy will make it possible to adapt the methods of conducting foreign policy to modern challenges and opportunities, to create conditions for the sustainable development of international relations, ensuring peace and stability in the world.

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